

Foreign Language Virtual Class Room: Anxiety Creator or Healer?

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Abstract

Virtual classroom using technology is a novel dimension in distance learning and teaching pedagogy during the pandemic situation across the globe. Researchers regard e-learning as an opportunity for future teaching and learning approach. Therefore, recent pieces of literature on Foreign Language Anxiety, Technological anxiety and E-learning using virtual classroom inspires the current researchers to foster a real picture of Bangladeshi educational institutions. The study aims at investigating whether the virtual classroom situation creates anything new in Foreign Language Anxiety or heals the learners from anxiety experienced in the physical classroom. A self-made Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLVCAS) was conducted through 104 students' participation from three public and three private universities of Bangladesh. Through the tertiary level learners' physical language classroom and virtual language classroom participation, the quantitative data has been collected. In-depth interview and focus group discussion have also been conducted to collect qualitative data. The study also shows findings and important recommendations for the concerned so that virtual language classroom environment and anxiety-free 'Foreign Language Virtual Classroom' can be implemented.

Keywords: virtual classroom, Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety, pandemic situation, learning environment, technology

1. Introduction

Emotional arousal and its impact in Second /Foreign language learning and acquisition have long been researched. Foreign language anxiety is a widely acclaimed research area in Second/Foreign language teaching. Besides, many of the previous studies record e-learning anxiety too. Few studies, on the other hand, recommended the use of technology in teaching as a coping strategy to reduce learning anxiety. Much of the previous research has been conducted on the aspect of anxiety and motivation. Anxiety has been recorded to have an impact on Language learning and acquisition. Most of the previous researches have reported Anxiety to affect negatively in language acquisition, though few types of research show that anxiety sometimes facilitates foreign language learning and acquisition. Language-learning stress has been defined as "the feeling of tension and apprehension specifically associated with second-language contexts" (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1994b, p.284). Spielberger (1983) terms anxiety as "the subjective feeling of tension, apprehension, nervousness, and worry associated with an arousal of the autonomic nervous system." Researchers, like Bailey, 1983; Horwitz, Horwitz, & Copes, 1986; MacIntyre & Charos, 1996, found many proofs that confirm anxiety has a negative correlation with the achievement in Second and foreign language and classroom situation, and teaching-learning system to be the source of study, one of the most important research by Stephen Krashen (1982) that begets 'Affective Filter Hypothesis' directs nonlinguistic variables to effect natural language flow. According to Krashen, "when language learners become anxious, a filter is raised in their minds which blocks linguistic input from entering"; this is known as the affective filter hypothesis (Krashen, 1981, 1982).

The present study has taken the initiative to see whether virtual classrooms using technology can heal some of the sources of anxiety or add more pressure to creating features. The study has been motivated by such types of research as anxiety. The use of technological gadgets in teaching has been recorded by Ramamoorthy (2016) to have a significant relationship regardless of the masculine and feminine, urban, and rural areas. On the other hand, few studies, for example, Al-Qahtani (2019), in his research, suggests that the role of virtual classes in enhancing communication skill is significant. Despite the potential of virtual courses in reducing learners' anxiety, Carr, Oliver, and Burn (2010) have shown that first-time users of a virtual environment may encounter a "pain barrier"

due to the “public and potentially intimidating nature of this virtual world” (p. 19). Anxiety experienced by language learners within the context of a virtual course may have the relation with the construct of computer anxiety that may happen due to fear of using computers as well as a confrontation to use them (Chua, Chen, & Wong, 1999; Lewis & Atzert, 2000). Studies on virtual learning focus less on language classroom and anxiety have also been under-researched. The challenging factor faced by the present researchers is that there is no virtual language classroom anxiety uniquely designed before. The researchers of the study attempted to prepare a virtual language classroom anxiety scale based on researchers’ personal teaching experience and previous Foreign language Anxiety scales and the experience. Technology Induce State Anxiety (TISA) measurement scale and technological gadgets using anxiety measurement scale administered by few researchers. The researchers administered their new “Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety scale”. The study and structured questions helped an in-depth interview and arrange a focus-group discussion to triangulate data and validate the research.

General Objective

This study investigates whether foreign language virtual classroom situation adds any features to Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety or heals it.

Specific Objectives

- To investigate the correlation between EFL classroom anxiety and learning language through virtual classroom.
- To make a Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety Scale.
- To find out whether the students feel easier in a virtual language classroom than physical classroom situations.
- To find the sources of Foreign Language virtual classroom Anxiety.
- To find out the features that help to heal Foreign Language classroom anxiety.
- To set recommendations for the concerned so that they may contribute to upgrading the virtual classroom atmosphere.

To carry out this analysis, the researchers have tried to answer the following questions:

Research Questions

1. Does language teaching using virtual platforms meet up learners’ demands in second language learning?
2. What are the features of the virtual classroom that create or heal Foreign language Classroom Anxiety?
3. How can virtual classroom among the tertiary level learners be possible to implement in the Bangladeshi private and public universities?

2. Literature Review

Vician (2004) claims that computer anxiety and oral communication apprehension adds to computer-mediated communication (CMC) anxiety, which subsequently impacts attitudes towards CMC and learning achievements.

In other studies, like Matsumura and Hann (2004) testified that employing technology in teaching causes apprehension, stress, and tension while intermingling with computers has backed to an increased level of learners’ anxiety.

On the other hand, Al-Qahtani (2019) conducted a study in the Female English Department at King Khalid University with thirty participants to investigate teachers’ and students’ perceptions of English as Foreign Language (EFL) virtual classes. The results of this study pointed out that the majority of the students and teachers possess a positive attitude toward teaching and learning through EFL virtual classes. The result suggests that the role of virtual classes in enhancing communication skills is significant.

Agogo and Hess (2015) have created a measure of technostress and validated in two different samples. The researchers introduced the Technology Induce State Anxiety (TISA) concept based on the Affective Response Model (ARM, Zao 2013 as cited in Agogo and Hess 2015). They have also introduced a negative affective variable by the recommendation of ARM.

Ramamoorthy (2016) develops and standardizes a scale to measure teachers’ technological gadgets using anxiety in teaching. The result of this study shows that the anxiety and use of technological devices in education have a significant relationship regardless of the masculine and feminine, urban, and rural areas.

The measures mentioned above inspired the researchers of the present study to create “Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety Scale” (FLVCAS)

Mokyr, Vickers, and Zeibarth (2015) conducted a study on the history of technological anxiety and the future of Economic growth. Though the study is not related to language learning, yet the idea that technology can be studied with anxiety inspired the researchers of the present study to carry out the study with virtual anxiety concerning language learning and teaching anxiety.

Paulina Sepu; Veda-Esobar, and Astrid Morrison (2020) conducted a study on online teaching placement during the Covid-19 pandemic in Chile mining at exploring the challenges and opportunities of virtual teaching experiences. The result of this study shows that the most negative and challenging factor is the lack of interaction with pupils, which might hinder their professional development. As this is not a real learning experience, they could not be able to gather real-life experience. Moreover, limited internet access is another cause of lack of connection between teacher and student, according to the pupils. Looking back to this study seems to the researchers of the present study is important because the challenges of the online learning system may provoke learners’ anxiety and may slow the achievement.

Peiwen and Yanling (2013), in their study regarding the connection between multimedia environments and English learning anxiety in EFL college students in Taiwan, found that Computer-assisted language learning instruction generates a non-threatening, positive and relaxed English learning environment’ which reduce learners language learning anxiety and stimulate their learning.

Hampel (2003, 2006) reveals that obscurity in online environments resulting from interaction in a Foreign language learning situation without verbal or visual indications might lead to a sense of isolation from others and increase learners’ anxiety.

Bohlin and Hunt (1995) accentuated that anxiety from computer use is context-dependent. They argue that the anxiety level of language learners may fluctuate in diverse contexts since doing the same tasks with computers; some learners may encounter an exalted degree of anxiety while others might experience low levels of anxiety. So, from the above discussion, it is clear that previous literature provides mixed decisions about the impact of technology use in teaching language in terms of creating learners’ anxiety, and the result may vary from context to context. The present research needs to investigate the correlation between technology-based virtual language classroom and learner’s Foreign Language Learning Anxiety considering in Bangladesh, especially in this pandemic situation. For this purpose, the present study has taken the following methods and procedures for the research.

3. Mixed Methods

Mixed methods of data collection have been used for the present study since the MM (mixed Method) approach seemed to be an appropriate way to be applied in this study because of its strength for addressing the research questions and the objectives of the present study. The researchers combined both quantitative and qualitative methods in the stages of data collection and data analysis. Qualitative data were collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The quantitative data collection covered the completion of a questionnaire named “Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety scale (FLVCAS)” made by the researchers. In this study, they conducted a close review and comparative analysis of the collected data from quantitative and qualitative sources.

The study used “Simple random sampling” while selecting the respondents. The target populations for the present study were the undergraduate students of three public and three private universities of Bangladesh who experienced virtual language class FLVCAS using Google Survey tools was served as a questionnaire to the participants (104 students from 6 Universities) through online, and feedback has also been collected. The survey was administered from June May 2020 to June 2020. The findings have been recorded, transcribed, and summarized. The students were from, University of Barisal, Shere-E-Bangla Agriculture University, Islamic University, Bangladesh Army University of Science and Technology, South-east University, Daffodil university of Bangladesh.

Eighteen participants from the questionnaire survey have been interviewed with eight selected open-ended questions to elicit qualitative data. The interview has been conducted through using the Zoom Meeting room, a virtual platform from June 2020 to July 2020.

Six students (One from each of the universities) were invited for virtual focus group discussions. The session was held on August 4, 2020, through using the Zoom meeting. The findings have been recorded, transcribed, and then, summarized.

In this study, triangulation is employed through the use of methodological triangulation by using three data collection instruments, i.e., Questionnaire survey, In-depth interview, and Focus group discussion. Multiple data sources using several tools, helped the present study obtain more accurate and reliable data.

A Mixed-Method (MM) approach combining the qualitative and quantitative methods was used for data collection and data analysis in this study. In the present study, the data were analyzed using google; the descriptive statistics were also used to analyze the responses of the participants.

4. Findings and Discussion

The result of the survey, in-depth interview, and focus group discussion has been presented in this section. The findings of data have been delivered according to research questions. Since previous literature could not offer a suitable FLVCAS, it became important to work on it. The study at the very beginning of its data collection made this Scale in the light of previous works related to the present study. In making this scale, the researchers used their experience in virtual language class experience, previous Foreign Language Anxiety scales, and Technology Related Anxiety scales. The researchers discussed with other language teachers and researchers of language education and piloted a study as an experiment taking limited use of the scale. The scale has been found to fulfil the objectives of the present research. The scale has been seen by the present study to satisfy the aim of the study, and it is easy to administer and thus reliable. It is a primary initiative and has the opportunity to be developed by future researchers. Table-1 shows the FLVCAS used by this study.

Table 1. Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety Scale

Sl.	Statements	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Strongly Disagree (4)	Disagree (5)	Total
Q.1	I have experienced virtual classes.						
Q.2	I have techno-phobia.						
Q.3	I feel easy in a real classroom environment						
Q.4	I feel easy to participate in language activities in front of teachers and classmates in a real classroom.						
Q.5	I feel easy to participate in the language activities in front of teachers and classmates in a virtual classroom						
Q.6	I feel isolated during virtual class						
Q.7	I feel much involved during real-life class.						
Q.8	I feel uneasy thinking that teacher or fellow students might see mine home setting						
Q.9	I feel fear to be disconnected during virtual class						
Q.10	I feel anxious thinking that the teacher does not see my non-verbal response and seriousness during the virtual class.						
Q.11	I feel fear of being recorded for every activity during virtual class						
Q.12	I feel safe during the virtual class since I do not have to give feedback standing before the whole level.						
Q.13	Since I do not have to expose my physical appearance in a virtual class, I feel comfortable, anxiety-free, and relaxed here.						
Q.14	Long time use of technology during the virtual class makes me anxious about my physical and mental health						

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- Q.15 The direct presence of eye contact with the teachers makes me more nervous than a virtual environment.
- Q.16 The virtual classroom setting makes me feel more suffocated than a real classroom
- Q.17 A real classroom setting makes me feel more suffocated than a real classroom
- Q.18 A real classroom environment fits me more for a language class. 104 responses
- Q.19 Virtual classroom environment fits me more for the language class
-

Results of the findings of each research question have been presented below:

For the sake of description, 'Strongly Agree' has been merged to 'agree' and 'Strongly disagree' have been incorporated to 'disagree.' As Q.1 deals with the basic questions to know whether the respondents have experienced virtual class, it has not been discussed under any research question. The result of this question has no significant disagreement to count.

R.Q-1: Does language teaching using virtual platforms ensure learners' demands in second language learning?

As shown in table no. 2, Q.3, Q.4, Q.7, and Q.18 of the Foreign language Virtual Classroom Anxiety Scale has been used to know about students' comfort in the physical classroom, whereas Q.5 ask directly about their comfort in the virtual language class. As a result, shows in Table 2, Responses to report their comfort in favour of real classroom is higher, whereas though a good number of students (45.2%) said that they also feel comfortable doing language activities in front of teachers and classmates in the virtual classroom. In comparison to the real language classroom, most students have reported that they feel more comfortable in entire language classrooms than the virtual platform.

Table 2. Survey result of the research question 1

Q.No	Statements	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Mean
Q.2	I feel easy in real classroom environment	81.7%	-	-	104
Q.3	I feel easy to participate in the language activities in front of teachers and classmates in a real classroom	58.6%	12.6%	28.8%	104
Q.4	I feel easy to participate in language activities in front of teachers and classmates in a virtual classroom.	45.2%	27.9%	26.9%	104
Q.5	I feel much involved during a real-life class	75%	7.7%	17.3%	104
Q.7	Real classroom environment fits me more for language class	77.8%	7.7%	14.4%	104
Q.18	Virtual classroom environment fits me more for language class	21%	37.5%	29.8%	104

Results of In-Depth Interview

The researchers have taken 12 respondents who previously filled up survey questionnaires. They were interviewed using the virtual platform (zoom meeting room). A comfortable and friendly environment has been ensured before the interview. One interviewer interviewed the student with both structured and unstructured questions, and another transcribed the responses for the record. The result has been summarized and presented below:

Only three among the twelve respondents have reported that they feel comfortable in a virtual language class as they think autonomous and thus comfortable in virtual classes. In contrast, the other nine said that virtual study could not be fruitful for language activities as it does not give them scope to do interactive activities. They feel tired as most of the levels become teacher dominated and network problem makes them miss important part sometimes. All of the respondents reported this problem. Though few of them do not miss group work, pair work, and other interactive activities, most of them said that lack of presence of these interactions makes the language

class boring, unfruitful, and thus uncomfortable. Imperfect language class makes them worry about their language achievements and thus become anxious.

Results from Focus Group Discussion

To collect data from an in-depth interview, a focus group discussion comprising six respondents (one from each university) has been arranged. The researchers invited debate based on findings of the in-depth interview. Students expressed their view about comfort and uncomforted in both the form of language classes. Most of the participants told that they feel isolated and uncomfortable in the virtual language classroom compared to the physical classroom environment as they do not feel the presence of their classmates and teachers. They miss group work, frequent interaction with the teachers and mates and pair work, and frequent responses as feedback, though one participant has reported that their teacher arranges group works in a virtual class. All the participants have agreed that less language achievement is ensured in the virtual classroom. To sum up, the discussion comes up with the decision that if a virtual classroom can arrange interaction like a real classroom, it could be less boring and ensure learning achievement.

Chart 1. Survey responses related to research question 1

R.Q-2: What are the features of the virtual classroom that create Foreign language Classroom Anxiety?

To confirm specific sources of Foreign language, virtual classroom anxiety of the Q.2, Q.6, Q.8, Q.9, Q.10, and Q.14 have been employed. The results have been shown in Table-3.

Table 3. Sources of Foreign Language Virtual Classroom Anxiety

Q.No.	Statements	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Frequency
Q.2	I have techno-phobia.	22.1%	53.9%	24%	104
Q.6	I feel isolated during virtual class	36.5%	34.6%	20.2%	104
Q.8	I feel uneasy thinking that teacher or fellow students might see mine home setting	45.2%	35.6%	19.2%	104
Q.9	I feel fear to be disconnected during virtual class	93.2%	-	-	104
Q.10	I feel anxious thinking that the teacher does not see my non-verbal response and seriousness during the virtual class.	68.2%	13.5%	18.3%	104
Q.14	Long time use of technology during the virtual class makes me anxious about my physical and mental health	68.2%	21.2%	10.6%	104
Q.16	The virtual classroom setting makes me feel more suffocated than a real classroom	40.4%	29.8%	22.1%	104

Results shown in the table confirm that most of the students do not have technophobia, and around half of the students having a sense of isolation and suffocation from the virtual language classroom setting. However, the other half disagreed with having these kinds of uneasiness. A good number of students reported feeling anxious, thinking that teachers and classmates may peep into their home setting. Respondents reported their sources of virtual classroom anxiety as to believe that teacher may not realize their seriousness and

non-verbal responses during virtual language class. Long-term use of technology for the virtual class also makes them anxious about their mental and physical health. The most important source of their virtual language classroom anxiety has been recorded as being the fear of being disconnected.

Chart 2. Survey responses related to research question 2

Results of In-depth Interview

Any source of virtual classroom anxiety found from the in-depth interview has been recorded. Repetition has been avoided in the presentation of the result. Thus, in-depth interview resulted in a few more sources of foreign language anxiety. Most of the participants of the interview have reported that lack of interaction makes them feel isolated and thus anxious during virtual language class. All of them are recorded to feel anxious in fear of being disconnected. Since they are bound to sit in a place for a long time, they are devoid of physical relaxation, making them mentally rigid. They feel a gap of bondage with teacher and classmates, which make them isolated, bored, and worried. Many of them think the fear of being recorded. They cannot see the teachers' expression, physical movement during communication. Many feel anxious about this because they think that they cannot follow their communication models in their best. One-way communication in most of the language class in the virtual classroom makes them feel monotonous and distracted in language activities. Almost all of them reported that network problems make them miss words or exact pronunciation from the teachers, which raises their listening anxiety. Some of them reported that in the real classroom, they could take help from the mates if they miss any point, but the virtual classroom does not give them a chance to do so, which makes them anxious. Most of them reported that they feel to be uncared by the teachers during the virtual language class.

Results from Focus Group Discussion

The debate was held on whether they feel isolated or not. Two of the participants have reported that they do not feel isolated as their teachers give feedback and one of them reported that they get a chance of group work. All have agreed that in comparison to the real classroom, they get less opportunity to be connected with classwork and feel less isolated. The focus group discussion decided that innovation from the teacher to make the class more interactive and engaging can make them feel easier, less isolated, and more successful. The debate also followed the fact whether they feel fear of being recorded. Most of the participants reported that teachers do not allow them to record the class. Only two of them reported having the chance. They are informed to feel fear in one sense as their mates or teacher can scrutinize and focus their fault, and, in another circumstance, they feel safe as they do not fear to miss anything of the lecture.

R.Q-3: How can virtual classroom among the tertiary level learners be possible to implement in the Bangladeshi private and public universities?

Questions that tell about anxiety healing factors in virtual language classroom directly and problems that deal with uncomfortable characteristics of physical language classroom have been considered for searching the answer to Research question 3.

Table 4. Anxiety healing factors of Foreign Language Virtual Classroom

Q.No	Statements	Agree	Disagree	Neutral	Frequency
Q.12	I feel safe during the virtual class since I do not have to give feedback before the whole class.	43%	27%	30%	104
Q.13	Since I do not have to expose my physical appearance in a virtual class, I feel comfortable, anxiety-free, and relaxed here.	60.5%	20.3%	19.2%	104
Q.15	The direct presence of eye contact with the teachers makes me more nervous than the virtual environment.	39.5%	42.2%	18.3%	104
Q.17	A real classroom setting makes me feel more suffocated than a virtual classroom	14.4%	44.3%	41.3%	104

Though a considerable number (30%) kept themselves neutral, Majority reported that as they are not compelled to stand before the whole class, they feel safe in the virtual class. It can be said that virtual class provides them with the opportunity to sit in relax, which reduces their learning anxiety too. It can be noted that in Bangladesh, the physical classroom becomes norm dependent and consequently rigid. The majority of the respondents reported that they feel comfortable, anxiety-free, and relaxed as they are not bound to expose their physical appearance in the virtual class. On the other hand majority of them disagreed to the point that nor does physical classroom setting makes them feel more suffocated than the virtual classroom, and neither do direct presence, or eye contact of the teachers make them more nervous than the virtual environment. In short, physical relaxation and not to lose their face in front of the physical classroom keep them relaxed in the virtual language classroom.

Results from the in-depth Interview

In-depth interview result for research question three reveals that the absence of direct communication and appearance in the class makes them feel safe. The chance of recording makes them assured that they will not miss anything from the lecture. The absence of extra pressure and the threat to maintaining classroom norms make the students feel easy in the language class. They can only concentrate on classroom activities.

The result from the Focus Group Discussion

Focus group discussion resulted that virtual language class brings flexibility to the class schedule; it is time and energy saving. Since it saves energy and time and brings flexibility, it helps to concentrate only on class. The features offered by digital technology make it easy to prepare for language activities.

In summary, it can be said that triangulated results from three research questions reveal that though the advantage of technology makes virtual classroom time and energy saving as well as easier to conduct, it lacks the necessary components of language class, for example, real-life practice, group work, pair work, and necessary interaction and these things make the learners feel isolated, uneasy, bored and thus become anxious about their language achievement. It makes most of the learners less comfortable in Foreign Language Virtual classroom than the physical/real one. Moreover, specific sources of their anxiety have been presented in the discussion above.

5. Recommendations and Conclusion

As findings reveal, teachers must have the innovation to make virtual language class more interactive. Teachers should care for them more so that they might not feel isolated and bored. The class should add pair work, group

work, and other interactive activities and take regular feedback. Teachers may consult the students who have techno-phobia to remove technology provoked anxiety. Authority should take the help of the government policymaker to upgrade the power supply and network so that students may feel safe not to be disconnected during class. Since the study has taken limited subjects for the study, it is recommended to conduct extensive research taking more issues from all sectors of education, and the FLVCAS has been primarily proposed for a related study. The study is seen to be much promising in Foreign Language Education research, which is expected to contribute to the up-gradation of Virtual language classroom Anxiety.

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Appendix

Dear Respondents,

This questionnaire seeks to obtain relevant data for the research titled “Virtual language classroom in new normal: Anxiety creator or healer?” intended for the current research to sort the anxiety area of virtual class. You are cordially invited to kindly contribute your ideas and opinions relevant to the study. While your participation in this study will facilitate the research, the information you share with the researchers would be kept confidential and be used only for the specific objectives of this work without any identification. Your participation in the study would affect you neither physically, financially, legally nor socially. You may withdraw yourself from the study any time without assigning any reasons.

For this purpose, the researchers have followed *i-Cart Scale* which include- “Strongly Agree”, “Agree”, “Neutral” “Strongly Disagree” or “Disagree”.

Sl. No.	Statements	Strongly Agree (1)	Agree (2)	Neutral (3)	Strongly Disagree (4)	Disagree (5)	Total
Q.1	I have experienced virtual classes.						
Q.2	I have techno-phobia.						
Q.3	I feel easy in real classroom environment						
Q.4	I feel easy to participate in the language activities in front of teachers and classmates in real classroom.						
Q.5	I feel easy to participate in the language activities in front of teachers and classmates in virtual classroom						
Q.6	I feel myself isolated during virtual class						
Q.7	I feel myself much involved during real life class.						
Q.8	I feel uneasy thinking that teacher or fellow students might see mine home setting						
Q.9	I feel fear to be disconnected during virtual class						
Q.10	I feel anxious thinking that teacher does not see my non-verbal response and seriousness during virtual class.						
Q.11	I feel fear of being recorded for every activity during virtual class						
Q.12	I feel safe during virtual class since I do not have to give feedback standing before whole class.						
Q.13	Since I do not have to expose my physical appearance in virtual class, I feel comfortable, anxiety-free and relaxed here.						
Q.14	Long time use of technology during virtual class makes me anxious about my physical and mental health						
Q.15	Direct presence or eye contact of the teachers makes me more nervous than virtual environment.						
Q.16	Virtual classroom setting makes me feel more suffocated than real classroom						
Q.17	Real classroom setting makes me feel more suffocated than real classroom						
Q.18	Real classroom environment fits me more for language class.104 responses						
Q.19	Virtual classroom environment fits me more for language class						

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